
THE CONCEPT OF MARK AND TYPES OF MARKS IN THE CORPUS
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In our article, we will focus on the concept of notation in the linguistic corpus and tell about its types. We give examples of several types of linguistic signs and ways of their creation.

Keywords: linguistic corpus, linguistic notation, types of notation.

The system of linguistic information provided to the text-forming units of linguistic corpora is based on linguistic theories defined in each branch of linguistic science. Linguistic information is obtained according to the current state of language development. That is, it is guided by the latest linguistic analysis. In addition, language corpora in electronic form aim to convey linguistic information as concisely as possible using specific, conventional notations.

Linguistic symbols included in language corpora serve not only as an information tool for language readers, but also as a reference source. In other words, the reader can not only get information about any linguistic unit through linguistic corpora, but can also use it as a single source necessary for research. Previously, scientific research was done by manual work such as collecting examples, writing on cards, collecting, grouping, and required long-term scientific research, but language corpora make such work as easy as possible. For example, in order to collect examples for previous scientific topics, the work of collecting examples from the works of many writers, newspapers and magazines was carried out for months and years. If language corpora containing linguistic information are created, the collection of such material can be done very quickly. Electronic corpora not only provide information about lexical units in the language (text), but can also provide information about each of its components. More precisely, it can represent lexical-semantic, grammatical (morphological, syntactic), and even phonetic features characteristic of each word in the language. The information potential of language corpora depends on the scientific and creative skill of its managers, creators, journalists-specialists and programmers. Because in the creation of language corpora, journalists-specialists are engaged in defining the linguistic character of each text unit, while a software engineer develops a mathematical algorithm for its management using computer programs. Language corpora in electronic form

can be created only on the basis of joint creative work of specialists in the field of such sciences.

Morphology is a science that studies the structure of words. For morphology, it is not important whether word particles express lexical meaning or not, because it considers all language units according to their formal structure. From the point of view of the content destination, only grammatical meanings are taken into account. For example, the substantive, critical, and quantitative meanings of words also belong to the grammatical meaning. Reporter-scientist S. Isaev called these meanings general grammatical meaning [1]. It is important to accurately define the classes of words that are grouped by their general grammatical meanings in morphological marking. Because the complete morphological image of words is directly related to the general grammatical meanings of words, i.e. word classes. If the notation regarding word classes is not set correctly, the notation of subsequent grammatical forms will also be created incorrectly.

Morphological designations for texts included in language corpora are based on the system of language analysis developed in this field. Because language corpora are an objective expression of language theory. Therefore, morphological designations should fully reflect the morphological system of the language. In connection with this, language analysis and electronic language markings used in language teaching are connected to each other.

A unit stored in a corpus is a word, a phrase, a sentence or a set of complete texts. For example, each linguistic unit in the texts included in the corpus, be it a single word or an addition, is given linguistic information. Providing such linguistic information in a language is called "annotation". (It was mentioned above). Since the word "annotation" itself means "brief content", the abstract of the linguistic units included in the corpus is also given briefly by conventional symbols. Such conventional signs, called "razmetka" in Russian,

are called "belgi-kod" and "beligelenim" in Kazakh. The complete nature of the linguistic information given to text units depends on the diversity of these designations. Notation represents linguistic details specific to individual levels in a language. Such signs can be semantic (lexical-semantic), morphological, syntactic. For example, in the National Corpus of the Russian language, words are divided into word class, declension, genitive (rod - muj., gen.), classification, animate-inanimate, verb and verb type, syllabary, etc. special morphological signs are given according to morphological characteristics. In the same way, it can be said that the necessary signs are placed in the text through semantic analysis.

It is said that phonetic, morphological, semantic, and syntactic markings are included in the scientific works written about the corpus of texts. But it is difficult to enter all these specifications at the same time during the construction of the case. Therefore, the introduction of linguistic designations in the corpora of foreign and Russian language education texts was carried out step by step. Corpus in which all these notations are set and complete linguistic information is provided are called "deeply annotated".

Among the special computer programs for natural language processing, the programs that automatically enter the mark into the text take a special place. Tagging, annotation can be said to be one of the most complex tasks, especially the size of the current corpus makes this work even more complicated. If a number of software tools called taggers and parsers are currently used to mark corpus texts at the morphological and syntactic level, the creation of automated systems for marking at the anaphoric and prosodic levels is not yet possible, and the main work is left to manual labor. As a result of computer programs that automate morphological analysis (taggers), each lexical unit in the text is "registered" with its grammatical characteristics. For example, lexical sign, lemma and grammemes (maternal-masculine gender, middle gender (this applies to the Russian language), accusative, animate/inanimate, ritual, stem, etc.). As a result of the work of the computer program for automated syntactic analysis, the characteristics corresponding to syntactic relations between words and phrases and syntactic units (sentence type, syntactic function of phrases, etc.) are provided.

But it cannot be said that natural language analysis is performed automatically without errors, because it usually offers several analysis options for one lexical unit (word, phrase, sentence). This is called grammatical homonymy. Eliminating such problems (morphological, syntactic) is one of the most important and complex problems in the field of computer linguistics. In order to eliminate such deviations (multiplicity, ambiguity) during the construction of cases, a semi-automated method is used, that is, the "error" of the computer is corrected by human intervention. This phenomenon of homonymy is also found in the Kazakh language. For example, the word black can be both a verb and an adjective.

In the Kazakh language, it is important to include the combination conditions that distinguish homonymy

in the program for automatic placement of morphological markings. By constructing a dictionary that shows the distribution of words, it is possible to find the relation of the words to the word class in the context. For example, in the Kazakh language, adjectives usually precede nouns. And verbs are often at the end of the sentence. That is, if the word after black is a noun, then black can be recognized as an adjective. (black dress, black hair). And if the word black is preceded by nouns in the adverbs of barys, income, expense, help, it can be recognized as a verb (look at the house, look at the child, look through the binoculars, look through the window).

So, tagging should be understood as the act of "attaching" specially accepted tags to text units. The tag here means: lexical, grammatical and other text elements for description at a purely linguistic level and for external extralinguistic (information about the author and information about the text: author, title of the work, year of publication and place of publication, genre, topic) level. are conventional symbols obtained.

Within the linguistic type of the sign, the following types can be distinguished: morphological, syntactic, semantic, anaphoric, prosodic, discourse, etc. All of these are implemented in accordance with the following principles:

1. Description (justification) of the designation drawing (scheme);
2. General system of linguistic concepts;
3. An analysis diagram familiar to the user (customer);
4. Motivation to enter parameters (motivation);
5. Theoretical neutrality (traditionality) of the label drawing;
6. Compliance with the international standard [2].

The only difference between a corpus and a set of texts in an electronic version is that the text contains a variety of linguistic information in a clear form. In accordance with this requirement, the idea of a specially marked (marked) corpus appeared in corpus linguistics. Label can be said to be the main characteristic of the case. By this characteristic, a corpus is distinguished from many simple collections of texts (or libraries of texts). The large number of signs related to the grammatical nature of the text increases the value of the corpus in the field of science and education. For example, three types of notation are widely used in the national corpus of the Russian language. The first is metatextual, that is, descriptions related to the general consideration of the text: the author of the text, the genre of the text, etc. features; the second and third - morphological and semantic descriptions: not looking at the text as a whole, but marking its grammatical features for each word using conventional signs (marking).

The non-linguistic form of the sign includes the following:

- 1) markup that represents text formatting features (headings, paragraphs, white space, etc.);
- 2) A label that represents information about the author and the text. At the same time, information about the author includes not only his name, but also his age, gender, years of life, etc. may be. And information

about the text, usually, except for the title, in which language it was written, year, place of publication, name, etc. The presence of such information in the corpus allows for a thorough search of the text base and, at the same time, they can be a useful tool for matching the relevant document. This is also called a meta tag.

Morphological designation.

In foreign terminology, part-of-speech tagging (POS-tagging) is used. Literally translated, in Russian it is *chasterechnaya razmetka*, and in Kazakh it is the marking of classes of words.

In fact, morphological features do not only define classes of words, but also include grammatical categories unique to that class of words. This is considered the main type of designation. This is because, firstly, most of the voluminous corpora are morphologically marked corpora, secondly, morphological analysis is considered the basis for further forms of analysis - syntactic and semantic notation, and thirdly, the achievements of computer morphology make it possible to carry out automatic marking of voluminous corpora with great accuracy.

Data about the mark is reflected in a certain structure and their types are as follows: lemma, word class mark, grammatical category mark.

According to the condition of the morphological marking diagram, firstly, it requires the existence of a set of tags (symbols), secondly, the existence of a description of each of them, and thirdly, the existence of a rule for matching tags (symbols) to text units. The size of the collection of symbols (tags) used in different corpora varies. Of course, the larger the set of symbols, the more complete the text analysis will be. But as the size of the corpus of texts increases, the number of morphological characters tends to decrease. The use of a simplified system of tagging makes it possible not to make too many mistakes, not to break disorder, morphological consistency, and to speed up the process of tagging a text consisting of millions of words.

In Russian linguistics, morphological identification is carried out in three stages: analysis (parsing); sorting; distinguish homonyms. Here, the method of linguistic (morphological) marking performed in the first stage is carried out according to the MUSTEM program. This program A.A. It is based on information from Zaliznyak's "Grammatical Dictionary of the Russian Language" and here the possible variants of the morphological features of each word form are written in zigzag brackets [3].

In the first stage, all possible variants of the word form are covered automatically, in the second stage, homonymous word forms are identified and question marks are placed next to them. This is also automatically loaded into GRAMBAT. In the third stage, identified homonyms, that is, lexical or grammatical meanings of the same word forms (it can be a word or a form of a word, i.e. grammatical forms), are searched from the texts, and which word class is determined manually, not automatically. And if there are languages that have found a solution to this problem, or to invent an algorithm that automatically separates homonyms, then there is no doubt that we need to exchange experience.

Let's give an excerpt from the text with automatic morphological marking according to the corpus of the Kazakh language:

"Edward Burnett Tylor, one of the scientists closely involved in cultural issues in the 19th century, made a conclusion" ("Obvious").

The automatic morphological tagging program analyzes this sentence as follows:

XIX/ XIX// [Lat]
 ғасырда/ғасыр/да/ [ЗТ/да/ЖС]
 мәдениет/мәдениет [ЗТ]
 мәселелерімен / мәселе/лерімен/
 [зт/лер/КЖ+i/ТЖ-3+мен/КС]
 тығыз/тығыз// [сн]
 айналысқан / айналыс/қан [ЕТ/қан/Е+АР+ЖЖ-3]
 ғалымдардың / ғалым/дардың/
 [ЗТ/дарКЖ+дың/ІС]
 бірі / бір/i [ЕС/i/ТЖ-3+АС]
 бірі/ бір/i [СА/i/ТЖ-3+АС]
 ағылшын/ағылшын [ЗТ]
 ғұламасы / ғұлама/сы [СН/сы/ТЖ-3+АС]
 Эдуард/Unknown
 Бернетт/ Unknown
 Тайлор/ Unknown
 тұжырым /тұжырым/ [зт]
 жасаған/жаса/ған/ [ЕТ/ған/Е+АР+ЖЖ-3]

Here Unknown is the unfound word. The missing word is a proper noun in this text. Basically, if a list of proper nouns were stored in corpus memory, information about the proper nouns already in memory would be provided. All other words are automatically lemmatized by the corpus program, as well as assigning conventional signs according to their word class and certain categorical meanings.

Syntax notation.

Nowadays, it is known that according to the requirements of the society, it is necessary to adapt any work to modern technology, simplify manual work, and automate science and education as much as possible. At the same time, language science is also focused on the most efficient use of technical capabilities. Since language is a means of human communication, the greater the thinking capabilities of the human brain, the more diverse the means of thought transfer. Speech (speech) is not only an organization of language tools, conveying a specific idea, but also intermingles with extralinguistic factors that show the communicative purpose of conveying ideas in its internal form. Concepts such as "discourse" and "pragmatics" have emerged as terms describing the forms of such expression and language communication, and language construction has begun to be studied from various angles. The period of preparation for communication before language exchange, communicative situations during language exchange are not directly reflected in the intralinguistic semantics of language tools. And the definition of extralinguistic factors is carried out through processes such as human thinking, brain activity, observation, feeling, and thinking. No matter how much the language fluctuates according to the purpose of the speaker in the process of conveying thoughts, the means of conveying thoughts

are subject to certain methods. That is, there are established syntactic structures for conveying ideas. For example, to express opposition to a certain action, the speaker uses "No", "can't", "can't", "doesn't", "wrong", "can't do it", "I'm against", etc. . uses similar syntactic structures. Therefore, there is a formula, a model that forms the essence of any language usage. The most difficult and complicated part of modeling linguistic units is that sentences are also built into certain syntactic relations.

The relevance of the theory of syntactic relations today is clearly seen in the construction of language corpora based on new scientific technology. Today's success of science and education requires the introduction of computer technology in all its fields. The traditional manual work of collecting material in scientific research is being automated today in connection with the creation of language corpora, and emphasis is being placed on simplifying the work performed by humans. At the same time, it is necessary to put the necessary material for scientific research into the computer memory, and to process large massive texts in accordance with linguistic requirements. Linguistic information stored in computer memory is used in linguistics under the term "mark" (label). They are divided into different types according to language levels. For example, according to the level of morphology (or type of analysis) - morphological notation, according to the level of syntax - syntactic notation, and there are many other types of notation. But these two are the main ones.

Among the linguistic features, the introduction of morphological features into the computer memory was

first undertaken in all languages. And since morphology deals with word particles, they are part of the language system. And the problem of entering syntactic markings into computer memory has not been solved in the same way in all languages.

Syntax notation is the result of syntactic analysis or parsing. This type of notation describes the syntactic relationship between lexical units and various syntactic constructions (for example, subject, verb phrase, etc.). And the connection of words in a sentence is not always stable. In compound sentences, the connection of words is not only in the words that are next to each other, but also in the space of several words. Such syntactic connections between words are called "derevozavisimost" in Russian linguistics in building corpora. "Vershina" is the main word that helps to connect words, while subordinate words are described as "vetva", i.e. branches [4].

In most cases, it is based on the structural grammar of direct constructors (grammar of structural components). The diagram of syntagmatic relations between the parts of the sentence is expressed in the form of a distribution of dependencies (dependency tree). In the text, they are indicated by open and closed brackets. Symbols (codes) describing various syntactic constructions are written in vertical brackets. Inside one double parenthesis is another double parenthesis, and so on. may enter, and the top-level element is the sentence marked with the symbol "S". Syntax-marked texts are recognized as "treebanks".

Compared to morphology, it can be said that the ways of representing syntactic structure and syntactic relations are not unified.

Figure 1 – An example of parsing (dependency grammar, ETP-3 system)

The syntactic analysis of the Russian language is often represented by the structure of dependence (tree dependence). Figure 3 shows the image of the English sentence "Long ago, in the city of Babylon, the people began to build a huge tower which seemed to reach the heavens soon" in the form of dependency distribution (tree dependency).

At the morphological level, as well as at the syntactic level, the process of reducing the refinement of the grammatical marking scheme is carried out in order to increase the speed and order of the text analysis. The method that emerged as a result of such a process was named skeleton parsing [4].

It is possible to insert syntactic marks into texts in the Kazakh language as well. However, syntax is not as amenable to modeling as morphology, meaning that automatic syntactic labeling is difficult. The process of adding syntactic marking to texts is often done manually. That's why syntactically marked corpora do not have a large number of words.

Since the syntactic system of a language is somewhat difficult and complex to model, syntactic features are not equally incorporated into the corpora of all languages, like morphological features. P.V., a well-known expert in corpus linguistics of the Russian language. Zakharov points out that "Unlike morphology, the method of representing syntactic structure and syntactic relations is not so unified" [2]. P.V. Zakharov says that syntactic analyzes can be conducted and modeled in several directions. In particular:

- grammatical relations or connections (grammar dependent);
- compositional grammar (grammar is directly composed);
- structural scheme grammar (grammar of structural schemes);
- traditional studies about the parts of the sentence (traditional syntactical studies about clauses);
- functional grammar (functional grammar);
- semantic syntax (semantic syntax, etc.) etc.

M.V. from the University of Helsinki. Corpus Linguistics Specialists of Kopotev and Petrozavodsk State University G.B. In his articles entitled "Principy syntaksicheskoy razmetki Helsinki annotirovannogo korpus russkikh tekstov Hanko", Gurin mentions various forms of syntactic markings to be included in the corpus, and states that markings can be introduced based on the analysis of traditional parts of speech, but some problems related to parts of speech in the language system have not yet been resolved. by saying, he concludes that it is impossible to model 100 percent of the signs related to the parts of the sentence [4].

The impossibility of complete automation of syntactic markings was shown by I.S. In his candidate's thesis entitled "Linguistic corpora with markup on the basis of grammatical dependencies and their application in automatic syntactic analysis", Chardin concludes as follows: "Many types of markup require the participation of expert linguists in the preparation of the corpus. This includes syntactic markup, which is a particularly labor-intensive type of markup. This is due to the fact that the accuracy of the results of preliminary

automatic syntactic marking is far from 100%, especially when distinguishing a large number of types of relationships" [5].

In syntactic marking, its minimum unit is not words, but syntactic units. They can be simple sentences or parts of sentences (predicative units) or clauses.

In corpus linguistics, a clause is the smallest sentence in a complex (compound) sentence, that is, sentence parts are subordinated to the verb in the sentence. It is called "vershina" in Russian language corpora. Based on the comments in the works written on Russian language corpora, in the absence of a verb, "vershina" is performed by another part of the sentence, which is a verb (narrator). Clauses also form connected and connected sentences, depending on the connection of the compound sentences. And the connection of clauses provided by place order and intonation (without interjections) is grouped as non-interjectional connection.

In syntactic models, it was decided to use a variant that divides the text into clauses, and other positions can be attributed to these variants. From a structural and formal point of view, the clauses can be expressed as follows. The text is first divided into paragraphs. It is formally separated by a new line. They are divided into sentences. A punctuation mark (period) is used to break up sentences. That is, a period and a capital letter identify individual sentences. And separate sentences are divided into internal parts. Thus, it appears as a set of parts. However, any of these parts is not considered a clause. Two situations should be considered:

- 1) each clause may consist of several parts within one sentence;
- 2) some parts of the sentence can be included in several clauses at the same time.

Therefore, a model of syntactic analysis is prepared during the compilation and research of corpora. According to this model, the sentences in the text are divided into sentence parts. And these parts are grouped into clauses. The order of the clauses is important. For example, let's take a sentence divided into 4 parts and mark it as Part1, Part2, Part3, Part4. If we combine Part1 and Part3, then Part3 and Part4 into clauses, we get the whole Part1-Part3-Part4 clause. If we combine Part1 and Part3 and then Part1 and Part4 into a clause, two clauses, Part1-Part3 and Part1-Part4, are created. Thus, communication is organized. It is said that any clauses can be extracted based on this algorithm.

The syntactic features included in the corpora of the Russian language are based on the above-mentioned relationship between words called "derevozavisimost". This is sometimes called "grammatical dependence". I.S. proved that the type based on syntactic relations is effective in automating syntactic analysis. Chardin also notes [5].

This approach to syntactic marking originates from the Prague Corpus. An annotated corpus of Czech texts compiled by Karlov at the University of Prague was created in 1998 and based on this position of grammatical communication. However, this corpus does not provide small groups of syntactic relations, but mainly shows only large groups. And according to Internet data, the corpus of the Russian language has 78 types

of syntactic relations, and the syntactic relations are more detailed than the Czech corpus. Such corpora based on grammatical connection include the German (NEGRA) and Dutch (Alpino) language corpora.

Syntactically annotated corpus texts of the Russian language can be divided into two groups. The first group consists of approximately 10,000 syntactically annotated sentences taken from fiction included in the well-known Russian Uppsala corpus. The second group consists of short texts of 30 sentences each from socio-political, cultural, economic, scientific and technical styles, the Internet, news on the Internet. This second group of texts describes the current state of the Russian literary language. According to the data of the Russian language, it is reported that texts consisting of 2000 sentences with syntactic annotation in the second group of styles are being entered.

Text labels are described by special markers. They are called "tags". Consists of tag-words and tag-containers. The first of these describes the words in the text, while the second describes the parts of the text.

When morphological marking, individual words in the texts are divided into root and suffix, and their grammatical description is given, while when setting syntactic marking, based on the principle of "derevozavisimost" used in the above Russian language corpora, the connection of words in separate sentences in the text is indicated and syntactic relations between them are described. For example, if we take a simple sentence "Оқушы мектептен шықты (The student left school)", the syntactically related words in the sentence:

Оқушы шықты.

Мектептен шықты.

The first of these phrases is based on the subject-predicate relationship, and the second shows an indirect object relationship. And there is no syntagmatic relationship between the phrase "student from school" in the sentence, therefore there is no syntactic relationship. This is because "the semantic connection between the components depends on the syntagms that make it up, their individuality" [6].

Since the development of syntactic notation is currently being developed in Kazakh linguistics, only the conditions for its development were mentioned above.

Semantic designation.

Any corpus of texts in the Kazakh language is equipped with annotation (grammatical signs of a conventional type), that is, any annotated corpus can determine the expression of its linguistic character. Typically, such a description should include a model of possible linguistic analysis of the units in the corpus. An annotated corpus is also valuable for its ease of use and multi-functional properties. In most cases, both automatic and "manual" types of corpus annotation are carried out simultaneously. And in order to consider the automated annotation operation as satisfactory, it will be necessary to take into account that the margin of error should not exceed three percent.

Semantic tags (conditional signs), in most cases, represent the semantic category to which the word or phrase in question belongs, and smaller categories that

differ in semantic tone. Marking of corpora at the semantic level considers distinguishing the meaning of words, solving the problems of homonymy and synonymy, categorizing (grouping) words, determining thematic groups, causative signs, evaluative and distributional (derivative) nature of words, etc.

Semantic signs are the division of words into lexical-semantic classes based on their belonging to different word classes.

Compilers of the National Corpus of the Russian language offer a version of the semantic markup specific to that language. In this corpus, three different symbols are attached to each word form:

1. Rank (personal name, personal pronoun, etc.);
2. Lexical-semantic characteristics (thematic group of the lexeme, causative signs, evaluations, etc.);
3. Derivational (distributive, word-forming) characteristics ("diminutive", "adjective adverb made from an adjective, etc.").

Lexical-semantic tags are classified into the following groups:

- taxonomy (thematic group of lexemes) - for nouns, adjectives, verbs and adverbs;
- mereology ("part - whole", "element - set") - to material and non-material names;
- topology (topological status of the designating object) - for object names;
- causation - for verbs;
- functional status - for verbs;
- evaluation - for nouns and non-nouns, adjectives and adverbs.

Verbal characteristics are divided into several types:

- morpho-semantic word-formative signs (for example, "caritive", "semelfactive");
- the form of the resulting word (for example, a noun formed from a verb or an adverb formed from an adjective (adjective);
- lexical-semantic (taxonomic) type of the resulting word (for example, an adverb formed from an adjective);
- morphological type of word formation (substantivization, compound word) (for details see: <http://ruscorpora.ru>, "Semantics" section).

In order to annotate the relationship of words to semantic groups in the Kazakh language in corpus texts, it is necessary to classify the lexical-semantic groups of each word class in the language system, and to describe all the words in the language according to their relationship to these groups. For that, it is necessary to determine the lexical-semantic groups of each word group and create a list of words belonging to that word group.

Phonetic notation.

Phonetic designations included in the corpus A. Based on Zhunisbek's 3-step guide [7].

A. In Zhunisbek's 3-step guide, the words in the text are described by three different signs. They are: the melody of the word, automatic division of words into syllables, phonetic description of sounds (letters). According to these signs, the following instruction was prepared for the program.

First step: Showing the melody (timbre) of the word. In the Kazakh language, words are divided into thick melodic and thin melodic depending on the thickness/thinness of the vowel sound. The program should automatically distinguish whether the words are thick or thin in the corpus. When suffixes are added to root words in Kazakh, they are added according to the thickness/thinness of the vowel sound in the word. Accordingly, it is defined as thick melodic or thin melodic word. In order for the program to automatically distinguish this sign, the following rule should be given. If the vowels in the first syllable of a word (or in a word) are thick vowels (**а, ы, ұ, о**), then this word is synharmonically considered thick melodic. If the vowels in the first syllable of a word (or in a word) are thin vowels (**ә, е, і, ө**), then this word is synharmonically considered thin melodic.

Second step: Divide the word into syllables and describe them. To describe the construction of syllables, the symbol of vowel/consonant sound in the international system is taken. They are: V (vocalism) - vowels; C (consonantism) - consonant sounds. In order to identify syllables based on sounds (letters), the computer program for phonetic notation should list and mark the letters of the Kazakh alphabet according to the above-mentioned V, C characteristics. For example: **А – V; Ә – V; Ы – V** etc. Similarly, consonants **П – C; Б – C; М – C** etc.

The types of syllables for the program of phonetic notation included in the corpus are described as follows (syllables are listed separately):

Vowel syllable - V (**а-на, о-тан, а-та, ә-ліп-пе, е-ді, ө-мір, ы-дыс, і-ні** etc);

Open joint - C+V (**ба-ла, қа-ла, бөл-ме, ә-ке, са-бақ** т.б.);

Closed joint - V+C (**ақ-ша, ақ-та-ды, ар-нау, өр-ле-ді, ор-на-лас-қан**);

Closed joint - V+C+C (**ант, айт-ты**);

Stop joint - C+V+C (**бай-лық, қой-ды, бер-ді, ә-кел-ді, та-быс, ең-бек, жаз-ды** т.б.);

Stop joint - C+V+C+C (**бұлт, қант, жалт, жырт-ты, құрт-ты** etc);

Stop joint - C+C+V +C (**Өз-бек-стан, Қа-зақ-стан** etc).

In order for the program to automatically segment words in the corpus, it will be necessary to provide instructions about the fixed positional lines of these syllables. For example, vowel V (**а-на, о-тан, а-та**) occurs only at the beginning of the word; C+V open syllable (**са-бақ, бер-ме-ді, бөл-ме**) occurs in all positions of the word; V+C closed syllable (**ақ-ша, ақ-та-ды, ар-нау**) is only at the beginning of the word; The closed syllable V+C+C (**ант, айт-ты**) is also found only at the beginning of the word; C+V+C stop syllables (**қой-ды, бер-ді, ә-кел-ді, та-быс**) remain in all lines of the word; C+V+C+C stop syllables (**бұлт-ты, жаң-ғырт-ты, жаз-дырт**) also exist everywhere; C+C+V+C stop syllable (**Өз-бек-стан, Қа-зақ-стан-да**) does not occur at the beginning of a word, it occurs in the middle of a word and at the end of a word.

The program automatically splits words according to this guide. And some words that come with "и" and "у" in the Kazakh language cannot be separated. For

example, going, coming, wrestler, variety, etc. Because in these words, the vowels before the u and i sounds are omitted. If these words were written as *барууы, келууі, балыуан, алыуан* the automaton would have been able to divide them freely according to the instructions given to the syllables [8].

The third step. The next phonetic description in the introduction of phonetic notation to the corpus is the analysis of sounds. For this purpose, a list is created for the program, describing the features of each sound (letter) according to the relation of the tongue, jaw, and lips. For example: А - ашық, тіларты, езулік; Ә - ашық, тілортасы, езулік; Ы - қысаң, тіларты, езулік; etc. [7].

Extralinguistic designation.

Corpses are divided into different subgroups (sub-corpus) related to their function. The compilation of annotated corpora with linguistic notation is especially important and useful for linguistic research. Depending on whether or not such annotations are made, corpora are divided into annotated (annotated) and non-annotated (not annotated) corpora. Although the construction of annotated corpora is important for linguistic research, it is first necessary to sort the texts to be included in the corpora and provide accurate information about them. This is sometimes called extralinguistic markup, and is also used as metatext markup (metatext markup - metamarkup). Linguistic markers are called internal markers, while metatextual markers are called external markers. They are: text and author information: author, title, year, place of origin, text genre, topic, style, size, etc. They are also divided into bibliographic, typological, thematic, social, formal (text, chapter, section, paragraph, sentence, etc.) and technical (performers, source from which the electronic version was obtained, date of editing, time of coding, etc.).

Extralinguistic designations or metadata include "external", "intellectual" designations (bibliographic description, typological description, thematic description, social description), "formal" structural designations (text, section, chapter, section, paragraph, sentence), as well as technical-technological designations (encoding, processing dates, performers, source of the electronic version). Metadata sets define the features of the data available to researchers in text corpora. Therefore, when selecting data, it will be necessary to be guided by the purpose of the study and the request of the reporters and the possibilities of introducing additional symbols into the text.

Metatext annotations are important information that should be included in any type of corpus, and linguistic annotations are performed before the construction of corpora, during the introduction of texts from different styles into the corpus.

Metatags are used in research works for a certain period, style, author, topic, etc. An indispensable resource for collecting related materials. From the corpora with metadata, researchers can select the style, period, author, etc. that they need. can quickly find information on information. And this success is undoubtedly

the only force that comprehensively develops the scientific research potential, science and knowledge of our modern developed country.

Regardless of the type of the corpus, first of all, the metatext parameters that provide information about the collected text must be entered into the computer database. Therefore, methods, types, computer programs, etc. of creating metadata (name of the work, author, year, place of origin, style, genre, volume, etc.) in the construction of the corpus. research is important.

There are theoretical positions and practical methods of metamarking in world linguistics. Theoretical and practical issues of metamarking in the national corpus of the Russian language were discussed by S.O. Savchuk considered [6].

There are several computer linguistic programs that allow metadescription of texts. He is primarily a Systematic Coder and UAM Corpus. The programs' data are freely accessible, free to use, and meet accepted standards in corpus linguistics. On the basis of this program, a metadescription architecture of texts in the corpora of different languages was created.

Word formation notation.

Word formation notation is a program for automatic recognition of derived words in the corpus. It differs from morphological designations - here the composition of root (derivative root) words is analyzed. If morphology separates the word-forming suffixes from the root and then analyzes them by assigning conditional designations to the suffixes of each modified form, then in the development of word-formation notation, the root of the derived word and the word-formation suffix are distinguished and it is determined

what word-formation suffixes those word-formation suffixes are. In our research work, we consider the combined words, double words, additional derived words, which are such word-forming units, and the methods and ways of marking them in the corpus (automatic recognition). For this, in the first chapter, we need to reveal the function of word-forming concepts and word-forming applications in the structural word-forming system of the Kazakh language.

«This research has been/was/is funded by the Science Committee of the Ministry of Education and Science of the Republic of Kazakhstan (Grant No. AP15473441)»

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